

THE INFLUENCE OF CULTURE ON LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract:

This article explores the intricate relationship between culture and language learning, emphasizing their profound interdependence in educational and linguistic contexts. The purpose of this study is to investigate how culture influences language acquisition processes and outcomes, with a focus on its role in shaping effective teaching practices and facilitating meaningful communication. Drawing on a comprehensive literature review, the article elucidates the inseparable connection between culture and language, highlighting the integration of cultural perspectives into language teaching methodologies. Ultimately, this research contributes to a nuanced understanding of the complex dynamics between culture, language, and language learning, informing pedagogical practices and guiding future research endeavors.

Keywords: language, culture, communication, impact, intersection.

Introduction

Nowadays, learning language is associated with culture, and it is more essential for effective learning and communication with people all over the world. Culture means beliefs, traditions, and behaviors, which play an important role in shaping society. We have an opportunity to communicate in various ways, such as sending and receiving messages with others. Scholars such as Greimas and Sapir point out that culture and its patterns involve communication. Culture includes everything ranging from food we eat to the way we interact with each other. However, language is also vital for interaction; it doesn't only mean words but also gestures, facial expressions, and so on. This article discusses how language and culture are closely related. Although they may seem separate, they are very much influenced by each other. Different parts of the world have different cultures and languages. Languages do not appear by themselves; their respective cultures shape them. The way a language develops can even influence its culture, and cultural ideas are often expressed through language. Also, language is not something we use to talk; it is also affected by society. So when we learn a new language, we also learn the culture associated with it.

Literature review

Salomeh (2018), like Kramsch (1), emphasizes the importance of the environment and conditions in which language is used effectively. Culture provides English Language Teaching (ELT) with a wide range of perspectives that can enrich classroom dynamics, especially among college students who choose specific fields of study. Salomeh noted that students may reject or ignore a teacher's lesson plan if they do not feel it is relevant to their chosen field of study. Thus, as Politzer (100-101) points out, teachers must be adept at using strategies to avoid presenting irrelevant images or symbols that may have unintended meanings for students.

Dimitrios Thanasoulas identifies two dominant perspectives that have influenced the integration of culture in language teaching. On the one hand, it focuses on the transmission of authentic cultural information, covering the institutional structures and other aspects of the target culture. This includes immersion in literature and art, as well as everyday cultural practices (Thanasoulas, 3).

Alyasery (2018) suggests from Wei (2005:56) that language serves as both a means of communication and a carrier of culture. They are inseparable from language and culture; each is a reflection of the other. Brown (1994:165) further emphasizes this interdependence between language and culture, arguing that language is part of culture and vice versa, and that separating the two diminishes the importance of both. This view is supported by Jiang (2000: 328), who argues that culture and language are inseparable.

Gao (2006) suggests that language learning is inherently a cultural learning process and therefore language teaching should include aspects of cultural learning. Similarly, Wang (2008) argued that teaching foreign languages essentially teaches foreign culture and makes language teachers into cultural teachers. Tomalin (2008) suggests that culture should be considered as a fifth language skill in English language teaching (ELT) along with listening, speaking, reading and writing. According to Tomalin, this fifth skill includes understanding and appreciating the norms, values, behaviors and skills of different cultures and using English as a means of communication.

Methods

In researching the impact of culture and language on students' English language learning, I conducted ethnographic observations to gain insight into their language learning experiences within their cultural context. I immersed myself in the student environment, spending time in classrooms, language rooms,

and social gatherings to observe their language learning activities and interactions. I took detailed field notes, recording students' language use, communication strategies, and cultural references. I also conducted interviews with students to explore the role of culture in shaping language learning motivations, challenges, and language acquisition experiences. In addition, I asked students to keep language diaries in which they recorded their thoughts about daily language learning activities and cultural influences. After collecting observational data, interview transcripts, and language diaries, I analyzed the data to identify recurring themes, cultural influences, and language learning strategies used by the students. By interpreting the results, I understood how culture affects students' language learning experiences and outcomes.

Overall, this observational approach provided valuable insights into the complex relationship between culture, language, and students' language learning processes, with potential implications for language teaching practices.

Discussion

Culture can be defined as a set of values, beliefs, and norms learned among a group of individuals (Greay, 1994). It covers various aspects such as ethnicity, nationality, gender, disability, race, sexual orientation and religion. Culture not only shapes people's values and behavior, but also influences their use of language. Understanding cultural nuances is essential to the achievement of linguistics, and language, in turn, can influence a society's culture.

For example, some archaic words may survive even when they are no longer used, reflecting cultural heritage. On the contrary, new words appear when they are associated with a specific cultural activity. Slang terms evolve over time and reflect changing societal trends. These linguistic changes are often influenced by various factors, such as television programs, politics, and music, which contribute to the formation of specific cultural trends. Examples of this phenomenon can be seen in the influence of popular music groups such as the Beatles and more recently in the emergence of Hip Hop culture.

According to the Project on National Standards for Foreign Language Education (1996), mastering a new language requires understanding its cultural context. In other words, success in acquiring a second language depends on understanding the related culture. This is analogous to the child's early experiences in his family, community, and environment, as Lu (1998) points out. Just as babies naturally acquire their first language through immersion in their environment, learners of a new language must absorb the cultural aspects associated with it.

As Stivick (1982) pointed out, teachers' perceptions of students' cultures can significantly influence the language learning process. Cultural awareness and cross-cultural training are essential for second language teachers. Providing students with cultural knowledge, introducing them to culturally rich environments, and offering culturally relevant materials can facilitate language learning. This is because familiarity with the target culture facilitates understanding and reduces learning difficulties.

As Lado (1957) points out in his *Linguistics Across Cultures*, significant differences between the second language and the learner's native language can cause difficulties. Thus, the similarity between the language being studied and the native language of the learner helps in language acquisition. Cultural support and understanding play a crucial role in bridging language gaps and facilitating learning.

Conclusion.

The complex relationship between culture and language highlights the central importance of studying their interaction in the fields of education and linguistics. Culture, which includes the beliefs, traditions, and social behavior shared by a group, profoundly shapes language learning processes and communication dynamics. As scholars such as Greimas and Sapir have pointed out, as social beings humans rely on language as their primary mode of communication, every cultural pattern and social behavior inherently involves communication. Language acquisition goes beyond memorizing vocabulary and grammar rules; it requires immersion in the cultural context behind the language. Understanding cultural nuances, such as different forms of address or communication styles, is critical to effective intercultural communication. Moreover, the symbiotic relationship between language and culture is evident in the evolution of linguistic expressions and the transmission of cultural ideas through language.

Scholars and teachers in the field of language teaching recognize the indispensability of combining cultural education with language pedagogy. Salomeh (2018), echoing Kramsch, emphasizes the importance of cultural relevance in language teaching, especially in meeting the diverse backgrounds and interests of students. Similarly, Alyasery (2018) and Gao (2006) emphasize the inseparability of language and culture, promoting cultural awareness and appreciation in language learning environments.

In practice, teachers use different methods to introduce cultural education in language teaching. From providing culturally relevant materials to engaging

students in culturally rich environments, teachers play an important role in developing intercultural competence and effective communication skills among language learners. By recognizing and embracing cultural diversity, teachers empower students to navigate linguistic and cultural differences with confidence and competence. Essentially, the integration of cultural education into language teaching and learning practices enhances students' language skills and promotes a deeper understanding and appreciation of different cultures. By recognizing the inseparability of language and culture, teachers pave the way for more inclusive and effective language education, preparing students to communicate confidently and competently in an increasingly interconnected world.

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